

MXene-assisted CoZnCr for efficient alkaline seawater splitting and anion exchange membrane electrolyzer

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Abstract: Designing efficient electrocatalysts for industrial-scale seawater splitting that can mitigate anodic corrosion while effectively driving oxygen evolution remains a significant challenge. Strategic surface engineering is crucial in developing electrocatalysts, bridging the gap between fundamental research and the practical demands of industrial water-splitting applications. In this work, we present the development of a CoZnCr@MXene heterostructure, which achieves a low cell voltage of 1.55 V at a current density of 50 mA cm⁻² and outperform RuO₂ in alkaline seawater electrolyte. The remarkable performance is attributed to synergistic enhancements arising from compositional tuning, surface engineering, and the integration of conductive supports, which collectively lead to substantial reductions in overpotentials for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) and hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). The CoZnCr@MXene catalyst exhibits excellent stability and selective oxidation in alkaline seawater, with MXene incorporation effectively suppresses chloride-induced corrosion while enhancing charge transfer efficiency. Furthermore, when employed in an anion exchange membrane (AEM) electrolyzer, the CoZnCr@MXene catalyst delivers a current density of 500 mA cm⁻² at an operating voltage of 1.72 V at 60 °C, corresponding to a cell efficiency of 77.8%. The calculated hydrogen production cost is \$0.86 per gallon of gasoline-equivalent (GGE), significantly below the 2026 technical target of \$2.00/GGE set by the U.S. Department of Energy. This work represents a significant breakthrough in the design of long-lasting, noble-metal-free electrodes for industrial-scale alkaline seawater electrolysis.

Introduction:

As a sustainable energy source, hydrogen has the potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from conventional fossil fuels and their negative effects on the environment. Water electrolysis is the most appropriate approach to generate high-purity hydrogen production since it can efficiently utilize solar and wind energy.^{1,2} So far, high-purity water remains the primary raw material for commercial electrocatalytic hydrogen generation. However, the global shortage of freshwater resources (approximately 3% of earth's water) demands the development of catalytic electrodes based on abundant metal elements for electrolysis of non-drinkable water sources.³ Seawater splitting is a prominent alternative as it makes up about 96.5% of the world's total water.⁴ One of the main advantages is that seawater, which makes up more than 70% of the Earth's surface, is readily available and offers an almost infinite supply of feedstock for electrolysis, allaying worries about freshwater shortages. It offers many benefits, such as the ability to produce green hydrogen, reduced competition with fresh water, and the utilization of a plentiful and renewable resource. With the added advantages of affordability, environmental sustainability, and scalability, seawater electrolysis offers a very promising way to meet the world's energy needs and help us move toward a sustainable, hydrogen-powered future.⁵

However, the dissolved ions in seawater, particularly chloride ions block the catalytic active sites and reduce the durability and efficiency of seawater splitting.⁶ The long-term stability and cost-effectiveness of seawater electrolysis systems are significantly hampered by corrosion, particularly when subjected to a harsh, salty environment for long periods. Although various current studies have focused on freshwater electrolysis, alkaline saltwater electrolysis is becoming more and more acknowledged as a practical and beneficial substitute, particularly considering the large and plentiful supply of seawater.⁷ Alkaline seawater electrolysis has emerged as a preferred method for seawater splitting, as it eliminates the need for a continuous alkali supply and effectively mitigates the anodic chloride oxidation reaction (COR).^{8,9} Recently, many researchers have focused on an anion exchange membrane (AEM) as the separator for seawater electrolysis. However, chloride ions (Cl^-) still appear to pass through the membrane towards the anode under the applied electric field. This results in the unwanted chloride oxidation reaction (CIOR) at the anode, which can cause degradation of the membrane. Therefore, it is essential to develop OER catalysts that have excellent salt tolerance in order to enhance the advancement of large-scale seawater electrolysis.

Lately, significant reports have been published on low-cost transition metal catalysts such as NiS^{10} , MoS_2^{11} and P-CoNiO_2^{12} for water splitting in an alkaline medium. Most of the catalysts are not suitable for industrial conditions due to the harsh conditions ($60\text{-}80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 400 mA cm^{-2}), bubble desorption and less occupancy of hydrogen bubbles at the active sites on the surface of electrocatalyst due to the inappropriate Gibbs-free energy.¹³ To withstand extreme working conditions, industrial electrocatalysts must fulfil

specific requirements such as low-cost materials with fast synthesis routes, active catalyst sites, suitable Gibbs-free energy and excellent chemical and structure stability.^{14,15,16} Layered double hydroxides (LDH) are the most promising candidates to match the above criteria as they exhibit high OER electrocatalysis.¹⁷ The unique structural design exposes the catalyst's active sites and enhances the electrochemical surface area of the OER electrocatalyst.¹⁸ For example, Fe, Co, Ni, Zn, and Mn-based LDHs have been studied widely for OER.^{19, 20, 21} Y. Gong et. al reported FeCo LDH for seawater electrocatalyst using a surface corrosion method, achieving the overpotential of 229 mV at a current density of 100 mA cm⁻².²² Y. Park et. al concluded that NiFeCo LDH based AEM alkaline seawater electrolyzer with potential less than 1.72 V can completely suppress the chloride evolution reaction (CIER) thermodynamically.²³ Therefore, developing efficient and durable electrocatalysts that allow for direct seawater electrolysis at low voltage is very desirable.

In this study, we present a highly efficient and stable CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ alkaline seawater electrocatalyst. The electrocatalyst has a high durability with a stable long-term performance in alkaline media with a low overpotential of 45 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² for HER, which is quite lower than that of Pt/C catalyst (58 mV). Similarly, the catalyst provided low overpotential of 47 mV at 50 mA cm⁻² for OER surpassing RuO₂ (93 mV). It required the cell voltage of 1.54 V and 1.62 V to reach current densities of 100 mA cm⁻² and 200 mA cm⁻² in an alkaline medium. In addition, the AEM alkaline seawater cell needs a cell voltage of 1.73 V to reach a current density of 0.6 A cm⁻², performing the state-of-the-art electrolyzer for seawater electrocatalysis. An AEM electrolyzer catalyzed by CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ electrocatalyst is stable over more than 17 days with a faradic efficiency of 100 %. The price of hydrogen (H₂) produced per gallon of gasoline-equivalent (GGE) is \$0.89, which is below the U.S. Department of Energy's (DOE) target of \$2.00 per GGE by 2026, suggesting superior application prospects. This work provides an optimal approach towards developing a highly efficient, corrosion and stable industrial scale catalyst at low potential for seawater electrocatalyst. It delivers a deeper understanding of the factors driving performance enhancement and offers valuable insights for the design of future catalysts.

Methods:

Chemicals:

Cobalt nitrate hexahydrate (Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O), zinc nitrate hexahydrate (Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O), chromium nitrate hexahydrate (Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O), 2-methylimidazole (C₄H₆N₂, 2-MIM), ruthenium (IV) oxide (RuO₂) and urea (NH₂CONH₂) were supplied by Lachema. Mo₂TiAlC₂, potassium hydroxide (KOH, Sigma Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), Pt/C (20 wt% Pt), sodium chloride (NaCl), Nafion (5 wt% Nafion polymer is dissolved

in a combination of lower aliphatic alcohols and water), methanol (CH₃OH), ethanol (C₂H₅OH) and hydrochloric acid (HCl) were purchased from Fluorochem. Nickel foam was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich.

Preparation of ZIF-67

Co(NO₃)₂ (894 mg) was dissolved in methanol (5 mL) and stirred for 10 min. 2-MIM (985 mg) was dissolved in methanol (30 mL) and stirred at room temperature for 10 min. Then, both solutions were mixed together and stirred at room temperature for 24 hr. The product was collected by centrifugation followed by repeated washings with ethanol and dried at 60 °C overnight.

Preparation of CoZnCr LDH:

The CoZnCr LDH was prepared using a hydrothermal method. Briefly, Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (150 mg), Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (50 mg) and urea (9 mg) were dissolved in ethanol (60 mL) and stirred for 5 min. ZIF-67 powder (50 mg) was added to the solution and stirred for 20 min. The mixture was transferred into a Teflon liner loaded in an autoclave and heated to 120 °C for 6 h. After cooling down to room temperature, the product was isolated by centrifugation using water and ethanol as dispersing media and dried at 60 °C overnight.

Preparation of LDH@Mo₂TiC₂ MXene:

For the preparation of LDH@Mo₂TiC₂, CoZnCr LDH (12 mg) was added to deionized water (10 mL), and stirred for 10 min. In another beaker, Mo₂TiC₂ MXene (1 mg) was added to deionized water (10 mL) and stirred for 10 min. Then, both solutions were mixed and stirred for 20 min. The solution was then centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 15 min. The product was collected and dried at 60 °C overnight.

Material characterization:

The structural and chemical analyses were performed by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) (Bruker D8, Cu X-ray source, $\lambda = 0.15418$ nm) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) (SPECS spectrometer equipped with a monochromatic Al K α X-ray source (1486.7 eV) and a hemispherical electron analyzer Phoibos 150). The morphology and composition of synthesized materials were examined using SEM/STEM (Tescan MAIA 3, Czech Republic) and HRTEM (JEOL 2200 FS, Japan). The detailed structural characterizations were examined using the transmission electron microscope (TEM) (JEOL 2200 FS (Japan)). The bubble contact angles were analyzed via ADVEX Instruments, Czech Republic

Electrochemical measurements:

Electrochemical measurements were performed using a potentiostat (Metrohm) with a three-electrode electrochemical system in a laboratory at room temperature. As for the preparation of the working electrode,

the catalyst powder (LDH@MXene, 3 mg) was mixed with Nafion solution (40 μL) and ethanol-water mixture (200 $\mu\text{L}/100 \mu\text{L}$), followed by sonication for 20 min to make an ink like solution and then dropped cast on Nickel foam ($1 \times 1 \text{ cm}$ active area) and dried at $\sim 60^\circ\text{C}$. For the preparation of Pt/C (40% Pt/C) and RuO₂ (3mg RuO₂), the same procedure was followed. The as-prepared electrode, Hg/HgO (1M KOH) and graphite rod were used as a working, reference and counter electrode for HER analysis respectively. For the OER measurements, platinum was used as a counter electrode. All potentials were converted to reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) using the Nernst equation ($E_{RHE} = E_{Hg:HgO} + 0.0591 + 0.098 \times pH$).²⁴ Before analysis, the sample was scanned with 20 cycles of cyclic voltammetry (CV) to reach stabilization. The linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) for HER and OER were recorded with the sweep rate of 10 mV s^{-1} under various electrolyte solutions (1M KOH, 1M KOH+NaCl (0M to sat. NaCl), 1M KOH+seawater, Natural Seawater). For comparison, linear sweep voltammetry of 40% Pt/C (for HER) and RuO₂ (For OER) were measured under 1M KOH. The Tafel slop was calculated from LSV using Tafel equation $\eta = b \log(j/j_0)$,²⁵ where η is overpotential, b is Tafel slop, j is current density and j_0 is exchange current density. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was obtained at a frequency range from 0.1 Hz and 100 kHz with an amplitude of 10 mV. The durability was measured at a constant current density of 100 mA cm^{-2} for 150 hr in three-electrode. The double-layer capacitance (Cdl) of the electrode was evaluated using cyclic voltammetry at different scan rates ranging from 10 mV s^{-1} to 100 mV s^{-1} . The sample names free-standing LDH and supported LDH indicate the CoZnCr and CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ respectively.

AEM electrolyzer fabrication:

The AEM electrolyzer was assembled using an anode (2.2 cm^2), a cathode (2.2 cm^2), and an anion exchange membrane. Both the anode and cathode were fabricated on nickel foam ($2.2 \times 2.2 \text{ cm}^2$) by directly depositing CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ catalyst at a loading of 4 mg cm^{-2} , forming a CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂||CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ AEM electrolyzer. For comparison, a RuO₂||Pt/C electrolyzer was prepared by depositing RuO₂ (4 mg cm^{-2}) onto nickel foam as the anode, while the cathode was prepared by applying Pt/C with Nafion onto nickel foam using the same method as the anode. The electrochemical performance of the AEM electrolyzer was evaluated using 1 M KOH and a 1 M KOH + seawater electrolyte, which was introduced into the AEM cell via a peristaltic pump at both room temperature and 60°C . Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) was performed at a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} . The long-term stability of the electrolyzer was measured via chronopotentiometry at a constant current density of 500 mA cm^{-2} over 410 hr. The internal cell temperature was maintained at 60°C by continuously circulating a preheated electrolyte (60°C) through the system. Faradaic efficiency (FE) was determined using the drainage method at a constant current density of 500 mA cm^{-2} in 1 M KOH + seawater.

Results and discussion:

Preparation and characterization of the CoZnCr LDH@Mo₂TiC₂ MXene

We used the self-assembly method to synthesize CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂, as presented in **Fig. 1** (see methods for detail). The scanning electron microscopy revealed a well-defined dodecahedral morphology (**Fig. 2a**).²⁶ Upon transformation of ZIF-67 into CoZnCr LDH, the initially smooth surface evolved into a nanosheet-clustered structure, as shown in **Fig. 2b**.²⁷ The incorporation of Mo₂TiC₂ MXene into CoZnCr-LDH preserved the nanosphere-like architecture of LDH while introducing nanoparticle-wrapped surfaces **Fig. 2c**.

Fig. 1 Schematic illustration of the synthesis process of CoZnCr@MXene.

To further investigate, the structural and compositional characteristics, scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) was employed, confirming the retention of the dodecahedral shape in CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂, as shown in **Fig. 2d**. Elemental mapping of Co, Zn, Cr, Mo, Ti, and C demonstrated a uniform distribution of elements throughout the composite (**Fig. 2e**). High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) revealed the presence of a distinct hollow nanocage structure, shown in **Fig. 2f, g**, in agreement with the SEM observations. The presence of hollow cavities within CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ serves as an electrolyte reservoir, enhancing the contact between electrolyte ions and the material, thereby facilitating electrochemical reactions.²⁸ The selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern (inset, **Fig. 2g**) further confirms the crystallinity of the synthesized composite. **Fig. 2h, i** depict well-resolved lattice fringes with interplanar spacing of 0.25 nm and 1.12 nm, corresponding to the (012) and (002) planes of LDH and MXene, respectively, which is further confirmed by the XRD²⁹. The XRD pattern of CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ aligns with the characteristic peaks of both Mo₂TiC₂ and CoZnCr, as presented in **Supplementary Fig. 1a, b**. Notably, the diffraction peaks at 31.7° and 36.2° correspond to the (012) and

(015) planes of CoZnCr, while the peak at 7.3° is indexed to the (002) plane of Mo₂TiC₂, consistent with the HRTEM results. The chemical state of CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ was investigated using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The Zn 2p spectrum exhibits two distinct peaks at 1023.6 eV and 1046.6 eV, corresponding to Zn 2p_{3/2} and Zn 2p_{1/2}, respectively, indicating the presence of Zn²⁺ (Supplementary Fig. 2a). Similarly, the Cr 2p spectrum displays peaks at 579.4 eV and 589.1 eV, attributed to Cr 2p_{3/2} and Cr 2p_{1/2}, respectively (Supplementary Fig. 2b), confirming the oxidation state of Cr in the composite.

Fig 2. SEM image of as prepared **a** ZIF-67. **b** CoZnCr. **c** CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂. **d** STEM image of as prepared CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂. **e** elemental mapping showing the uniform distribution of Co, Zn, Cr, Mo, TI and C. **f**, **g** HRTEM image of CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂. **h**, **i** Lattice fringes of CoZnCr and Mo₂TiC₂.

The deconvolution of the high-resolution spectrum of the Mo 3d region suggests the presence of Mo in two oxidation states, Mo⁴⁺ and Mo⁶⁺, respectively. The peaks at 231.0 and 234.2 eV correspond to the 3d_{5/2} and 3d_{3/2} components of Mo⁴⁺, respectively, and the peaks at 234.7 and 237.7 eV correspond to the same components of Mo⁶⁺ Supplementary Fig. 2c.^{29, 30} The XPS C 1s spectrum reveals peaks at 286.9 eV, 285.7 eV, and 282.2 eV, which are assigned to C–O, C–C, and Mo(Ti)–C bonds, respectively (Supplementary

Fig. 2d). Additionally, the O 1s spectrum displays peaks at 532.4 eV and 534.0 eV, corresponding to Mo–OH and O–C species, respectively, as shown in **Supplementary Fig. 2e**.

Electrocatalyst for alkaline electrolysis

Half-cell performance of CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ electrode

The electrochemical performance of the CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ electrode was evaluated using half-cell water electrolysis in a 1.0 M KOH electrolyte.

Fig 3. Electrochemical performance. **a.** HER polarization curves of CoZnCr@MXene, CoZnCr, ZIF-67, Pt/c and Ni foam in 1M KOH. **b.** Tafel slopes of the five electrocatalysts-HER. **c.** OER polarization curves of CoZnCr@MXene, CoZnCr, ZIF-67, RuO₂ and Ni foam in 1M KOH. **d.** Tafel slopes of the five electrocatalysts-OER. **e.** comparative overpotential of three different electrocatalyst at various current densities. **f.** Polarization curves of overall water splitting (OWS) in 1M KOH. **g. i.** Contact angles (static water-droplet) for CoZnCr@MXene and Ni foam. **ii.** Digital photos demonstrate the hydrogen release behavior. **h.** Long-term stability test at 100 mA cm⁻².

To assess the HER activity, linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) measurements were performed for various catalysts. CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ demonstrated superior HER performance, exhibiting a low overpotential of 45 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² and 141 mV at 100 mA cm⁻², outperforming ZIF-67 (297 mV at 100 mA cm⁻²), CoZnCr (208 mV at 100 mA cm⁻²), and commercial Pt/C (214 mV at 100 mA cm⁻²), as shown in **Fig. 3a**. Additionally, the CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ electrode exhibited a Tafel slope of 90 mV dec⁻¹, which is suggesting that the rate determining step is the Heyrovsky pathway. Additionally, the obtained value is lower than that of Pt/C (112 mV dec⁻¹), indicating enhanced HER kinetics and superior catalytic efficiency compared to the commercial 40% Pt/C catalyst (**Fig. 3b**). Furthermore, CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ achieved significantly higher current densities of 500 mA cm⁻² and 1000 mA cm⁻², surpassing commercial Pt/C, which highlights its potential for industrial applications (**Supplementary Fig. 3a**). Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis of CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ demonstrates its efficient charge transfer, as indicated by its low charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) of 4.17 Ω, which is lower than that of commercial Pt/C (5.53 Ω), as shown in **Supplementary Fig. 3b** (inset: equivalent circuit diagram). The electrochemical surface area (ECSA) of the catalyst was determined by measuring the double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}) from cyclic voltammetry (CV) scans at different scan rates. CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ exhibits a significantly higher C_{dl} of 22 mF compared to CoZnCr (11 mF), indicating a larger ECSA and a greater number of electrochemically active sites (**Supplementary Fig. 4a-d**). Beyond HER, the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) plays a crucial role in water electrolysis. The OER catalytic performance of different electrodes was evaluated under identical conditions as HER. As shown in **Fig. 3c, d**, the CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ electrode exhibits outstanding OER activity, requiring a low overpotential of 47 mV to achieve a current density of 50 mA cm⁻², with a Tafel slope of 47 mV dec⁻¹. These values are significantly lower than those of RuO₂ (93 mV), highlighting the superior OER kinetics of CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂. For comparison, the overpotential and Tafel slope values of recently reported OER electrocatalysts are summarized in Supplementary Table S1. **Fig. 3e** presents the overpotential required at various current densities for different catalysts, highlighting the superior HER activity of CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ across the entire current density range. Notably, at a high current density of 500 mA cm⁻², CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ requires an overpotential of only 339 mV, which is significantly lower than that of the commercial 40% Pt/C catalyst (497 mV). This remarkable performance underscores the exceptional catalytic efficiency and robust stability of CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂, particularly at high current densities, making it a promising candidate for practical electrocatalytic applications.

The CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂||CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ electrode exhibits outstanding overall water-splitting performance, requiring a remarkably low cell voltage of 1.48 V at 50 mA cm⁻² and 1.40 V at 10 mA cm⁻². This performance surpasses that of the commercial Pt/C||RuO₂ electrode (1.58 V) and represents one of the best values reported to date (**Supplementary Fig. 5 and Table S2**), as illustrated in **Fig. 3f**. The wettability

of the electrode surface plays a crucial role in catalytic performance, particularly at high current densities, as it influences mass transport and electrolyte penetration. To assess this, the contact angle (CA) of a water droplet on the electrode surface was measured. As shown in **Fig. 3g (i)**, the CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ electrode exhibits a significantly smaller contact angle of 65°, indicating superior wettability compared to Ni foam (114°). Enhanced wettability improves the electrode–electrolyte interface, facilitating better electrolyte infiltration and mass transport.^{31, 32} Furthermore, hydrogen bubble release observations reveal that large bubbles formed on Pt/C electrodes in compare to CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ (**Fig. 3g(ii)**), which indicates variations in gas release behavior. Larger bubbles on Pt/C suggest delayed detachment, potentially due to surface wettability or bubble adhesion forces. In contrast, smaller bubbles on CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ imply more efficient bubble detachment and dispersion, which can enhance reactant diffusion to the catalytic surface. However, these differences do not affect intrinsic reaction kinetics, which are governed by thermodynamics and catalyst conductivity. The long-term operational stability of CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ for overall water splitting (OWS) was evaluated in a two-electrode system under alkaline conditions (1 M KOH). As shown in **Fig. 3h**, the cell voltage remains nearly unchanged over 150 hr of continuous operation, demonstrating remarkable durability and stability at high current densities. This outstanding long-term performance highlights the robustness of CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ as a promising electrocatalyst for practical water-splitting applications.

Salinity test of catalyst

The electrocatalytic activity of the CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ electrocatalyst was systematically investigated in an alkaline electrolyte with varying NaCl concentrations (ranging from 0 M to saturation). Remarkably, the catalyst maintains excellent HER and OER kinetics even in a saturated NaCl solution, as illustrated in **Fig. 4a, b**. For the HER, the overpotential exhibits a slight increase of 53 mV when transitioning from 0 M to saturated NaCl, indicating stable catalytic efficiency in saline conditions. Similarly, for the OER, the overpotential increases from 68 mV (0 M NaCl) to 131 mV (saturated NaCl), demonstrating a moderate variation of 63 mV (**Fig. 4c**). These results demonstrate the catalyst's remarkable salt tolerance and electrochemical stability. Notably, its catalytic performance is stable with increasing salt concentration, consistent with the experimental observations, underscoring the potential of CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ for electrocatalytic applications in saline and seawater environments. The cyclic stability of the CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ catalyst was evaluated by comparing the linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) curves for HER and OER before and after 10,000 cycles in a 1 M NaCl + 1 M KOH electrolyte. As shown in **Fig. 4d**, the CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ catalyst demonstrates stable catalytic performance, with only a 19 mV increase in overpotential for HER and a negligible 6 mV increase for OER (**Fig. 4d inset**) at a current density of 10

mA cm^{-2} . Furthermore, the long-term stability of the $\text{CoZnCr@Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2$ catalyst was assessed using a chronopotentiometric (CP) test at a current density of 90 mA cm^{-2} under various salt concentrations.

Fig 4. **a.** LSV curves of CoZnCr@MXene for the HER in different salt solutions. **b.** LSV curves of CoZnCr@MXene for the OER in different salt solutions. **c.** Corresponding histogram of overpotential (HER, OER) at 10 mA cm^{-2} . **d.** Polarization curves of CoZnCr@MXene before and after 10,000 cycles for HER, inset: LSV curves for OER before and after 10,000 cycles. **e.** Chronopotentiometry curves for OER in 1.0 M KOH with 1 M NaCl and Sat. NaCl at 90 mA cm^{-2} .

In the 1 M NaCl electrolyte, no significant loss in current density was observed over 70 hr of continuous operation, highlighting the catalyst's excellent resistance to salinity. Notably, the catalyst maintained outstanding durability without any noticeable degradation, even in a saturated NaCl electrolyte over 40 hr test, further demonstrating its superior durability (**Fig. 4e**). These findings highlight the $\text{CoZnCr@Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2$ electrocatalyst as a promising candidate for seawater splitting applications, owing to its high corrosion resistance, excellent salt tolerance, and long-term stability.

Electrocatalytic seawater performance of the catalysts

Seawater electrolysis presents a cost-effective and abundant alternative to freshwater electrolysis; however, its suitability as an electrolyte for efficient electrolyzer operation must be carefully evaluated.³³ In this study, the electrocatalytic activity of $\text{CoZnCr@Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2$ for overall water splitting was assessed in both $1 \text{ M KOH} + \text{seawater}$ and natural seawater. The catalyst exhibited cell potentials of 1.55 V and 1.58 V to achieve a current density of 50 mA cm^{-2} in $1 \text{ M KOH} + \text{seawater}$ and natural seawater, respectively, as shown in **Fig. 5a**. Notably, the cell potential required in natural seawater (1.58 V at 50 mA cm^{-2}) is

significantly lower than that of the Pt/C||RuO₂ electrode (1.69 V at 50 mA cm⁻²), as seen in **Supplementary Fig. 6a**. The CoZnCr@MXene catalyst exhibited overpotentials of 73 mV (HER) and 150 mV (OER) in 1 M KOH + seawater, and 86 mV (HER) and 214 mV (OER) in natural seawater, demonstrating superior HER and OER kinetics compared to other catalysts, as shown in **Supplementary Fig. 6b, c**. These results demonstrate the potential of CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ as a promising electrocatalyst for seawater electrolysis, with excellent performance in both HER and OER under practical, seawater-based conditions.

Fig 5. Catalytic performance in different electrolytes: **a.** LSV curves of CoZnCr@MXene||CoZnCr@MXene catalyst in various electrolytes at 26 °C. The polarization curves of CoZnCr@MXene||CoZnCr@MXene for overall water splitting at different temperatures, **b.** In 1M KOH, **c.** In 1M KOH+seawater. **d.** A cell potential of CoZnCr@MXene||CoZnCr@MXene to reach 100 mA cm⁻² current density in 1M KOH and 1M KOH+seawater electrolyte. **e.** The HER overpotentials of the CoZnCr@MXene electrocatalyst to achieve current densities of 10-200 mA cm⁻² in various electrolytes. **f.** EIS curves, **g.** Chronopotentiometric curve at 50 mA cm⁻² in 1M KOH+seawater and natural seawater. **h.** Overpotential and long-term stability compared with the literature. The Tafel slopes and long-term stability data are from references (Supplementary Table S5).

The typical operating temperature for industrial water electrolysis systems ranges between 50 and 90 °C to reduce the total voltage required for water splitting.³⁴ To bridge the gap between laboratory conditions and commercial applications, the electrochemical performance of CoZnCr@MXene was evaluated at these temperatures in a three-electrode system. As the temperature of the alkaline and alkaline seawater electrolytes increased from 26 °C to 90 °C, the voltage required for water splitting decreased, as shown in **Fig. 5b and c**. At elevated temperatures, CoZnCr@MXene achieved a current density of 1000 mA cm⁻², outperforming Pt/C||RuO₂ (**Supplementary Fig. 6d**). The catalyst facilitated overall water splitting with a cell voltage of 1.52 V at 26 °C in 1 M KOH + seawater at a current density of 100 mA cm⁻², as shown in **Fig. 5d**. When comparing the cell voltage at 100 mA cm⁻² in 1 M KOH and 1 M KOH + seawater, only an additional 0.09 V (at 26 °C) was required in the seawater electrolyte, highlighting the potential of CoZnCr@MXene for industrial water electrolysis applications. **Fig. 5e** demonstrates the overpotentials of CoZnCr@MXene to achieve current densities of 10, 50, 100, and 200 mA cm⁻², showing only a 10-20 mV change across four different electrolytes at particular current density (**Supplementary Table 3**) confirming its efficacy in alkaline, saline, and seawater electrolytes. Furthermore, CoZnCr@MXene exhibits a low charge transfer resistance of 4.74 Ω in 1 M KOH + seawater, further emphasizing its rapid reaction kinetics (**Fig. 5f and Supplementary Table 4**). Chronoamperometric measurements demonstrate the excellent durability of the CoZnCr@MXene catalyst, with minimal cell voltage decay over 100 hr of continuous operation in 1 M KOH + seawater and 60 hr continue operation in natural seawater, as shown in **Fig. 5g**. Additionally, the decreasing cell voltage for natural seawater indicating improved energy conversion efficiency of water splitting. The CoZnCr@MXene catalyst demonstrates significantly faster reaction kinetics and exceptional stability compared to other reported non-noble metal catalysts (**Fig. 5g and Supplementary Table S5**). Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP-OES) analysis of electrolytes shows very low concentrations of Zn, Cr and Mo ions after the long stability test, confirming negligible leaching and demonstrating the material is effectively resistant to corrosion and oxidation (**Supplementary Table S6**). Post-test scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images (**Supplementary Fig. 7a**) show that the CoZnCr@MXene catalyst retains its surface morphology, further confirming its robust structural integrity. The catalyst exhibits outstanding corrosion resistance against chloride ions and other complex ionic species present in seawater, along with superior structural stability at high current densities. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of the post-OER electrodes shows negligible changes in peak positions across various planes, further supporting the chemical stability of CoZnCr@MXene under seawater conditions (**Supplementary Fig. 7b**). Additionally, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis (**Supplementary Fig. 7c**) reveals a positive shift in all peaks, which is indicative of enhanced OER kinetics.^{35,36} These findings suggest that the CoZnCr component plays a pivotal role in providing resistance

to chloride-induced corrosion,^{37,38} contributing to the catalyst's efficient catalytic activity and outstanding stability for alkaline seawater electrolysis.

Mechanism understanding

To gain a deeper understanding of the relationship between the catalyst and its electronic structure, density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed on model structures of CoZnCr and MXene. The results reveal a relatively low number of antibonding states in CoZnCr@MXene, which further supports the stability of the computational model (Supplementary Fig. S8 a,b). The electronic coupling between CoZnCr and Mo₂TiC₂ (Supplementary Fig. 9 a-f). The results demonstrate that hybridization between

Fig 6. a. Projected density of states for CoZnCr on Mo₂TiC₂ with surface terminations of CoZnCrO₄H / Mo₂TiC₂O₂, **b.** Free energy profiles of HER for free-standing and supported CoZnCr on Mo₂TiC₂ with different surface terminations with optimized structure for HER inserted image. (Note: The results are obtained at external potential $U_{\text{ext}} = 0.0$ V), **c.** free energy of adsorbed H* intermediates (ΔGH^*) on CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ and CoZnCr, **d.** Charge transfer between CoZnCr and Mo₂TiC₂ with different surface terminations. The blue and violet iso-surfaces shows electron and hole accumulations, **e.** Optimized atomic structures for OER, **f.** Free energy profiles of OER for free-standing and supported CoZnCr on Mo₂TiC₂ with different surface terminations (Note: The results are obtained at external potential $U_{\text{ext}} = 0.0$ V).

CoZnCr and Mo₂TiC₂ leads to charge redistribution, shifting the density of states near the Fermi level and enhancing the catalytic activity of active sites. The total density of state (DOS) analysis shows that CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂ has a larger electron density around the Fermi level compared to CoZnCr (Fig. 6a and Supplementary Fig. 10a,b). The results imply that the thorough restructuring of the catalyst boosts its

electrical conductivity, allowing for efficient electron transfer in electrocatalysis. To determine the most favourable surface-active site for each intermediate step, we compared the adsorption energies across different surface sites. In the case of HER (Fig. 6b), the Gibbs free energy values of the key intermediates (*H) on freestanding LDH are positive, with a minimum barrier of 0.4 eV. It is evident that the presence of MXene significantly influences the HER energy barrier of heterostructure compared to the freestanding CoZnCr (see Table S7). The CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂(OH)₂ exhibits the lowest energy barrier among the different considered surface terminations, suggesting high catalytic activity for HER. Moreover, the free energy of hydrogen adsorption (ΔG_{H^*}) is a key parameter influencing HER performance, with a value close to zero suggesting optimal H adsorption and efficient H₂ release. The calculated ΔG_{H^*} value for CoZnCr@ Mo₂TiC₂ is 0.06 eV, which is nearer to the thermoneutral point compared to the values for CoZnCr (0.39 eV) (Fig. 6c) indicating a surface that facilitates the efficient desorption of the evolved hydrogen species. Notably, hybridization is more pronounced in the case of CoZnCr and Mo₂TiC₂O₂, resulting in the highest charge transfer and interfacial binding energies, as shown in Fig. 6d and Table S8. This strong interaction effectively lowers the energy barrier for *OOH formation, the rate-limiting step, further improving OER efficiency. The structural configurations of intermediates (Fig. 6e) reveal that Cr atoms serve as the most favourable adsorption sites for stabilizing intermediates during the OER process. Free energy profile calculations (Fig. 6f) indicate that the rate-limiting step in supported heterostructures corresponds to the transformation of [O*] to [*OOH], consistent with a previous report³⁹. However, the overpotential is lower than that of freestanding LDH under similar conditions, suggesting faster OER kinetics on CoZnCr@Mo₂TiC₂. Thus, the incorporation of Mo₂TiC₂ modifies the Gibbs free energy landscape of the HER-OER pathway and tunes the electronic structure of the catalyst resulting in enhanced HER and OER activity.

Performance of an AEM seawater electrolyzer

We further assembled an alkaline seawater AEM electrolyzer utilizing CoZnCr@MXene as both the anode and cathode, as depicted in **Fig. 7a**. The polarization curve for overall water splitting in 1 M KOH + seawater reveals that the electrolyzer requires a cell voltage of 1.64 V to achieve a current density of 100 mA cm⁻² at 26°C, which is significantly lower than the commercial Pt/C||RuO₂ electrolyzer (1.77 V) under the same current density, as shown in **Fig. 7b**. This demonstrates that the CoZnCr@MXene-based AEM electrolyzer outperforms commercial electrocatalysts in terms of efficiency. Additionally, using a drainage gas collection method, the O₂ gas production from the CoZnCr@MXene electrolyzer was measured (**Supplementary Fig. 11a, b**), yielding a Faradaic efficiency of 99% in alkaline seawater electrolyte, as shown in **Fig. 7c**. The catalyst also exhibited exceptional durability, maintaining a stable performance at a current density of 200 mA cm⁻² for 16.8 days, with negligible cell voltage degradation, indicating

outstanding stability and high selectivity for alkaline seawater electrolysis, as demonstrated in **Fig. 7d**. Furthermore, the CoZnCr@MXene||CoZnCr@MXene-catalyzed AEM electrolyzer exhibits a cell efficiency of 77.8%, surpassing the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) target efficiency of 77%, at a current density of 0.2 A cm^{-2} (**Supplementary Fig. 11c and Supplementary Note 1**). Additionally, a critical metric of the electrolyzer's economic viability is the hydrogen production cost, which is calculated to be as low as \$0.86 per GGE of H_2 , as detailed in **Supplementary Note 1**.

Fig 7. AEM electrolyzer performance in alkaline seawater. **a.** Schematic illustration of AEM electrolyzer. **b.** Polarization curves of CoZnCr@MXene||CoZnCr@MXene in 1M KOH+seawater at 26 °C and 60 °C with Pt/C||RuO₂. **c.** FE of producing O₂. **d.** Durability test of the CoZnCr@MXene||CoZnCr@MXene AEM electrolyzer in 1M KOH+Seawater electrolyte at 200 mA cm^{-2} .

This value is less than half of the DOE's 2026 target of \$2.00 per GGE, demonstrating the potential for economical hydrogen production.⁴⁰ These results highlight a promising pathway for the efficient and cost-effective production of H_2 and O_2 via seawater electrolysis, facilitated by outstanding catalytic activity and stability. This remarkable performance can be attributed to: (1) the unique nanocage architecture, which facilitates optimal interface interaction and creates a high density of active catalytic sites; (2) the synergistic interplay between the catalyst's hierarchical structure and compositional attributes, which enhances the

interfacial electron transfer between active sites and the substrate, thereby significantly improving the intrinsic catalytic activity; and (3) the chloride ion resistance of CoZnCr@MXene, which minimizes Cl⁻ interference, promotes the H₂O-OH⁻ reaction pathway, and ensures selective catalysis.

Conflict of Interests

There are no conflicts to declare.

Conclusion:

In summary, we successfully developed a CoZnCr@MXene electrocatalyst for selective, efficient and highly stable alkaline seawater electrolysis at higher current densities. The hierarchical hollow structures enhance the diffusion of reactants and products to and from the catalytic sites. Increasing the number of such sites lowers the overall activation energy; and promotes efficient electron transfer, facilitating faster charge transfer and reaction kinetics. The catalyst displays a good HER and OER performance with a low overpotential of 45 mV and 20 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² in an alkaline medium respectively. Notably, the catalyst exhibits an impressive performance, with an overpotential increase of less than 63 mV as the salt concentration in the electrolyte increases from 0 M to saturated NaCl. Moreover, CoZnCr@MXene exhibits a low cell voltage of 1.60 V at 100 mA cm⁻² current density in alkaline seawater electrolyte higher stability for electrocatalytic seawater OER. The CoZnCr@MXene AEM seawater electrolyzer achieves high performance with a cell voltage of 1.83 V at 1000 mA cm⁻² at industrial conditions with high cell efficiency of 77.8 % and durability over 16.8 days (0.2 A cm⁻²) in alkaline seawater electrolyte. Moreover, the DFT calculations revealed that MXene plays a crucial role in enhancing HER and OER performance by significantly improving electroactivity, strengthening adsorbate binding, and facilitating efficient electron transfer. The result outperforms reported articles in seawater electrolysis. The results provide important insights for effective electrolyzer design and a strategic approach to catalyst development for seawater electrolysis with low energy consumption.

Data Statement:

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the study are accessible via the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15100523>

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